

Original Research

Erigeron sumatrensis (Asteraceae): a new alien species to the flora of Kosovo

Bujar Kadriaj¹, Naim Berisha^{1*}

Abstract

Erigeron sumatrensis is a South American annual weed that has become widely established outside its native range, including much of Europe and the Balkan Peninsula. Despite its regional distribution, the species had not previously been confirmed for the flora of Kosovo. This study documents the first verified record of *E. sumatrensis* in Kosovo and provides initial data on its distribution and habitat preferences. Field surveys conducted in 2025 across a broad range of habitats recorded the species at least 29 localities, primarily along roadsides and highways, urban margins, construction sites, waste ground, abandoned fields and disturbed agricultural areas. Additional occurrences along riverbanks and alluvial corridors indicate an ability to extend beyond strictly anthropogenic habitats. Species identification was based on diagnostic morphological characters and comparison with regional floras, with voucher specimens deposited in the Herbarium of the University of Prishtina (UPH). The widespread occurrence of *E. sumatrensis* suggests that the species is already well established in Kosovo. Given its known invasive behaviour and its strong association with transport corridors and disturbed environments, early monitoring and management measures are recommended to limit further spread and potential ecological and agricultural impacts.

Keywords

Alien flora; Compositae; Biodiversity; SE Europe

¹ Department of Biology, Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, University of Prishtina, Kosovo

* Corresponding author:

E-mail address: naim.berisha@uni-pr.edu

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Erigeron sumatrensis (Asteraceae): nova tuja vrsta v flori Kosova

Izvleček

Erigeron sumatrensis je južnoameriška enoletna plevelna rastlina, ki se je široko razširila zunaj svojega izvornega območja, vključno z večjim delom Evrope in Balkanskega polotoka. Kljub regionalni razširjenosti ta vrsta doslej ni bila potrjena v flori Kosova. Ta študija dokumentira prvi potrjen zapis *E. sumatrensis* na Kosovu in zagotavlja začetne podatke o njegovi razširjenosti in preferencah glede habitata. Terenske raziskave, izvedene leta 2025 na širokem spektru habitatov, so zabeležile vrsto na vsaj 29 lokacijah, predvsem ob cestah in avtocestah, na obrobju mest, gradbiščih, zapuščenih zemljiščih, opuščeni poljih in motenih kmetijskih območjih. Dodatni pojavi ob rečnih bregovih in aluvialnih koridorjih kažejo na sposobnost širjenja tudi izven strogo antropogenih habitatov. Identifikacija vrste je temeljila na diagnostičnih morfoloških značilnostih in primerjavi z regionalno floro, z vzorčnimi primerkami, deponiranimi v herbariumu Univerze v Prištini (UPH). Široka razširjenost *E. sumatrensis* kaže, da je vrsta že dobro uveljavljena na Kosovu. Glede na njeno znano invazivno vedenje in močno povezanost s prometnimi koridorji in motenimi okolji se priporočajo zgodnji ukrepi spremljanja in upravljanja, da se omeji nadaljnje širjenje in potencialni ekološki in kmetijski vplivi.

Ključne besede

Tujska flora; Compositae; Biotska raznovrstnost; Jugovzhodna Evropa

Introduction

Biological invasions represent one of the main drivers of global biodiversity change and have intensified significantly in recent decades. Alien plant taxa can alter ecosystem functioning, reduce native biodiversity, disrupt nutrient cycling and cause substantial agricultural and economic losses, especially in human-modified landscapes (Vilà et al., 2011; Pyšek et al., 2012; 2020; Seebens et al., 2021). Europe has seen a continuous increase in the arrival and establishment of invasive alien plants, with many species expanding rapidly due to climate change, land-use transformation and intensifying transport networks (Essl et al., 2011; Riera et al., 2021).

Within this broader context, the Balkan Peninsula is regarded as a region of high ecological sensitivity to biological invasions due to its heterogeneous landscapes, intensively used agricultural areas and climatic gradients that favour the establishment of disturbance-adapted alien taxa (Lambdon et al., 2008; Šilc et al., 2012). Several alien plant species have already become naturalised or invasive across the region (Kalusová et al., 2024), raising concerns about their ecological and socio-economic impacts.

The genus *Erigeron* L. (Asteraceae), comprising more than 458 accepted species worldwide (POWO, 2025),

includes several globally invasive taxa. Among these, *Erigeron sumatrensis* Retz. (syn. *Conyza sumatrensis*) - Sumatran fleabane has become one of the most successful invaders in tropical, subtropical and increasingly temperate regions (Galkina & Vinogradova, 2020). Native to South America, the species has invaded Europe, North America, Australasia, Asia, and Africa, establishing particularly dense populations across roadsides, croplands, wastelands, and other disturbed habitats (Rasool et al., 2016; Cheng et al., 2025). The invasion success of *E. sumatrensis* is attributed to high fecundity, efficient wind dispersal, extended germination periods, rapid growth and high tolerance of environmental variability (Hao et al., 2009; Bellache et al., 2022). In agricultural systems, the species is a highly invasive weed that competes with crops such as soybean, cotton, and cereals, causing significant yield losses (Wang et al., 2018; Bellache et al., 2022; Lorenzetti et al., 2025). Effective management has become increasingly challenging because the species has developed resistance to multiple herbicides, including glyphosate, paraquat, diquat, and ALS inhibitors, across several continents (Florentine et al., 2021; Heap, 2025).

In Kosovo, 21 invasive alien plant species have been documented to date (Kadriaj et al., 2023; Kadriaj, 2024), with two additional alien species recently recorded (Millaku et al., 2024). Although this number appears comparatively

low, it most likely reflects the still-limited systematic assessment and monitoring of alien flora in the country rather than the actual extent of biological invasions. The genus *Erigeron* is represented by two invasive alien species: *E. canadensis* (syn. *Conyza canadensis*) and *E. annuus*, but no verified records of *E. sumatrensis* (syn. *Conyza sumatrensis*; *Conyza albida*) existed until now. Given its invasive behaviour elsewhere and its potential for rapid spread once introduced, documenting its presence is crucial for early detection and management.

The aim of this study is to report the first confirmed occurrence of *E. sumatrensis* in Kosovo, describe its habitat characteristics and provide initial field observations that form a baseline for future monitoring and management of invasive alien species in the region.

Materials and Methods

Field surveys to detect the presence of *Erigeron sumatrensis* Retz. in Kosovo were conducted between spring and late autumn of 2025 across a wide range of habitats, including lowland agricultural areas, urban and peri-urban zones, roadside corridors and hilly to sub-montane environments (Figure 2, 1–C). Survey sites were selected based on known disturbance gradients, where invasive alien plant species typically establish and spread. For each locality where the species was observed, coordinates and altitude were recorded. When populations were encountered, representative individuals were photographed in situ and subsequently sampled. Collected material was pressed, dried, mounted, and deposited in the Herbarium of the Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, University of Prishtina (Herbarium acronym: UPH).

Specimens were identified using standard European floras and regional taxonomic keys for the genus *Erigeron*. Diagnostic characters were compared with descriptions in authoritative works, including Flora of Croatia (Nikolić, 2020) and regional floras. Particular attention was paid to characters distinguishing *E. sumatrensis* from the morphologically similar species *E. canadensis* and *E. bonariensis*, such as leaf morphology, capitulum structure, pappus length and stem indumentum (Figure 1 – A, B). The most reliable characters distinguishing *E. sumatrensis* from the morphologically similar *E. bonariensis* and *E. canadensis* are the architecture of the synflorescence, relative length of peduncles, involucre indumentum and colouration,

capitulum width and ligule conspicuousness (Table 1), as derived from critical comparison of the examined material with relevant taxonomic literature (Marshall, 1973; Tutin et al., 1976; Davis et al., 1988; Vladimirov et al., 2016; Nesom, 2018). All verified records were compiled with their geographic coordinates. Spatial data were processed and visualised to produce a distribution map showing confirmed occurrences of *E. sumatrensis* in Kosovo.

Results and Discussion

Erigeron sumatrensis Retz. (Asteraceae) (Figure 1) is a rapidly spreading annual plant native to South America that arrived in Europe in the late 19th century, with the earliest confirmed record from 1875 in France (Pruski & Sancho, 2006). Its expansion accelerated during the 20th century, reflecting the broader continental trend of increasing alien plant introductions linked to globalisation, land-use change and intensifying propagule pressure (Pyšek et al., 2009; Chytrý et al., 2009). Today, *E. sumatrensis* is established in all Balkan countries, with published records from Albania (Baltisberger & Lippert, 1987), North Macedonia (Vladimirov et al., 2016), Serbia (Vrbničanin et al., 2004), Bosnia and Herzegovina (Maslo & Šarić, 2020), Croatia (Čarni, 1996; Milović, 2004), Bulgaria (Vladimirov, 2009; Vladimirov & Petrova, 2023), Greece (Baliouisis, 2014), Montenegro (Stešević & Petrović, 2010; Stesević et al., 2014), Slovenia (Čarni, 1996; Poldini & Kaligarić, 2000), Romania (Anastasiu & Memedemin, 2012; Sîrbu et al., 2023), and European Turkey (Davis et al., 1988). Despite its widespread regional presence, no verified occurrence had previously been documented for Kosovo, making the present findings the first confirmed national record.

Our field surveys conducted throughout 2025 indicate that *E. sumatrensis* is already widely distributed in Kosovo, occurring in at least 29 localities ranging from lowland agricultural zones to hilly-submontane belts (Figure 2). These records likely represent only a fraction of its actual range, as the species was frequently encountered opportunistically outside targeted sampling plots. The most common habitats are roadsides (Figure 1–C), urban edges, construction sites, waste grounds, abandoned fields, and disturbed agricultural soils. These patterns are fully consistent with European-scale assessments showing that ruderal, arable, urban, and traffic-associated habitats exhibit the highest levels of alien plant invasion (Chytrý et

Figure 1. *Erigeron sumatrensis* Retz. (Asteraceae). A. Capitula at fruiting stage showing pappus-bearing achenes; B. Leafy stem with characteristic narrow, pubescent leaves; C. Typical habitat in Kosovo, with dense populations established along highway embankments. Photos by: Naim Berisha (A, B), Bujar Kadriaj (C).

Slika 1. *Erigeron sumatrensis* Retz. (Asteraceae). A. Cvetna glavica v fazi plodovanja, ki kaže plodove s perjem; B. Listnato steblo z značilnimi ozkimi, dlakavimi listi; C. Tipično življenjsko okolje v Kosovu, z gosto populacijo ob avtocestnih nasipih. Fotografije: Naim Berisha (A, B), Bujar Kadriaj (C).

al., 2009). High propagule supply, recurrent disturbance, and nutrient enrichment make these habitats ideal sites for initial establishment.

Beyond anthropogenic environments, *E. sumatrensis* was also found in semi-natural habitats, notably along riverbanks and gravelly alluvial corridors. Riparian zones are recognised as among the most vulnerable natural ecosystems to alien plant invasion due to continuous disturbance, high nutrient loads and effective hydrochorous transport,

with watercourses acting as efficient vectors for the downstream dispersal of propagules (Zelnik, 2012; Chytrý et al., 2009). The occurrence of *E. sumatrensis* in such habitats in Kosovo illustrates its capacity to move beyond strictly human-modified zones, indicating an early stage of naturalisation within riverine ecosystems. In nearly all localities, the species co-occurred with *Erigeron canadensis*, another well-established neophyte, suggesting similar ecological niches and dispersal pathways.

Figure 2. Distribution of recorded localities of *Erigeron sumatrensis* Retz. in Kosovo. Red circles indicate sampling sites
 Slika 2. Porazdelitev zabeleženih lokalitet *Erigeron sumatrensis* Retz. na Kosovu. Rdeči krogi označujejo mesta vzorčenja.

Patterns observed in Kosovo also reflect broader land-use and biogeographical gradients. According to the recent biogeographical regionalisation of Kosovo (Berisha et al., 2025), the species is primarily concentrated in the Continental regions, where urbanisation, road infrastructure and agricultural activity are most pronounced. These areas exhibit the highest propagule pressure, reinforcing the strong link between human activity and early invasion dynamics. Occasional occurrences in the foothills of the montane region indicate the possibility of future upward expansion along valleys and river systems, a pathway well documented for other invasive neophytes in Europe (Pattison et al., 2016). However, given its predominantly sub-Mediterranean to warm-temperate ecological affinity,

upward expansion into higher montane zones may be constrained by climatic conditions, particularly lower temperatures and shorter growing seasons.

Dispersal pathways in Kosovo align with general invasion patterns observed elsewhere in Europe, where wind dispersal enables background spread, while secondary, often anthropogenic, vectors play a crucial role in accelerating range expansion (Higgins & Richardson, 1996). In Kosovo, these vectors likely include vehicle-induced air turbulence, roadside management, and the transport of soil, gravel, and construction materials. River corridors serve as additional conduits, particularly during flood events, which transport diaspores downstream into newly disturbed substrates (Zajac et al., 2011).

Tabela 1. Diagnostic morphological characters distinguishing *Erigeron sumatrensis*, *E. bonariensis*, and *E. canadensis*.Table 1. Diagnostične morfološke značilnosti, ki razlikujejo *Erigeron sumatrensis*, *E. bonariensis* in *E. canadensis*.

Character	<i>E. sumatrensis</i>	<i>E. bonariensis</i>	<i>E. canadensis</i>
Plant height	50–180 (–200) cm	Up to 250 cm	10–150 cm
Stem colour	Greyish-green	Grey-green	Green
Stem indumentum	Densely pubescent with two types of eglandular hairs: short appressed hairs & scattered longer patent hairs	Densely hirsute, often with longer spreading hairs	Sparsely patent-hirsute to nearly glabrous
Leaf shape	Lanceolate to narrowly lanceolate or elliptic-lanceolate; remotely dentate	Linear to linear-oblongate	Lower oblanceolate and petiolate (often deciduous); upper linear
Upper leaves	Sessile, densely pubescent	Narrow, densely hairy	Linear, less hairy
Synflorescence outline	Rhombic to narrowly pyramidal	Broadly pyramidal to funnel-shaped	Narrow, elongated panicle with a dominant central axis
Side branches of synflorescence	Not overtopping the central axis	Usually overtopping the central axis	Strictly shorter than the central axis
Involucre length	4–5 mm	4–6 mm	3–4 mm
Involucral bracts	Densely pubescent, greyish-green, often reddish at apex	Densely hirsute, often purple-tipped	Glabrous or nearly so
Pappus length & colour	4–5 mm, Pale brownish	4–6 mm, Dirty white	3–4 mm, Whitish
Capitulum width	3–6 mm	Often 1 cm or more	Less than 1 cm
Ligules	Shorter than 0.5 mm, inconspicuous	Up to 0.5 mm	0.5–1 mm, Whitish and conspicuous

Although impacts have not yet been quantified for Kosovo, studies from other regions demonstrate significant ecological consequences of *E. sumatrensis* invasion, including suppression of native early-successional flora, alteration of competitive dynamics and interference with agricultural productivity (Hao et al., 2009; Liendo et al., 2021). In Slovenia, Zelnik (2012) documented substantial biodiversity reduction in invaded riparian habitats, a pattern likely to be mirrored where *E. sumatrensis* forms dense stands.

Overall, our results indicate that *E. sumatrensis* is already spreading rapidly across Kosovo. Its affinity for disturbed, nutrient-rich and traffic-associated habitats, combined with its capacity to enter semi-natural riverine systems, positions it as a potentially aggressive invader with the ability to expand further. Given the accelerating rate of alien plant introductions in southeastern Europe (Pyšek et al., 2009) and the high ecological sensitivity of river corridors and agricultural systems, early monitoring and targeted management will be essential to prevent further spread and potential ecological impacts.

This study documents the first confirmed occurrence of *Erigeron sumatrensis* in Kosovo and shows that the species

is already widespread across various habitat types. Its rapid expansion, effective dispersal mechanisms, and ecological flexibility highlight the urgent need for early detection, long-term monitoring, and coordinated management strategies. As Kosovo continues to urbanise and experiences increased movement of goods, soil and construction materials, the risk of further spread remains high. Integrating this species into national invasive plant monitoring frameworks is therefore essential to mitigate potential ecological and agricultural impacts.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization: NB, Methodology: NB, BK, Investigation (fieldwork): NB, BK, Data curation: BK, Formal analysis: BK, Resources (herbarium material): NB, Writing – original draft: BK, Writing – review & editing: NB, BK, Visualization: BK, Supervision: NB.

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Data Availability

The research data is available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18750518>).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- Anastasiu, P., & Memedemin, D. (2012). *Conyza sumatrensis*: A new alien plant in Romania. *Botanica Serbica*, 36, 37–40.
- Baliouis, E. (2014). Recent data from the flora of the island of Limnos (NE Aegean, Greece): New alien invasive species affecting the agricultural economy of the island. *Edinburgh Journal of Botany*, 71(2), 275–285.
- Baltisberger, M., & Lippert, W. (1987). Compositen aus Albanien. *Candollea*, 42, 679–691.
- Bellache, M., Torres-Pagan, N., Verdeguer, M., Llinares, J. V., Benfekih, L. A., Sestras, R. E., ... Boscaiu, M. (2022). Comparative analysis of tolerance to salt stress and water deficit in two invasive weeds of the genus *Erigeron* (Asteraceae). *Plants*, 11(15), 2059.
- Berisha, N., Krasniqi, E., & Bytyqi, V. (2025). Biogeographical regionalization of Kosovo: Integrating vegetation, climate and topography. *Mediterranean Botany*, 46(1), e99744.
- Čarni, A. (1996). Thermophilous vegetation of trampled habitats in Istria (Croatia and Slovenia). *Biologia*, 51, 405–409.
- Cheng, H., Johansen, K., Jin, B., Xu, S., Zhao, X., Han, L., & McCabe, M. F. (2025). Human footprint with machine learning identifies risks of the invasive weed *Conyza sumatrensis* across land-use types under climate change. *Global Ecology and Conservation*, 61, e03657.
- Chytrý, M., Pyšek, P., Wild, J., Pino, J., Maskell, L. C., & Vilà, M. (2009). European map of alien plant invasions based on the quantitative assessment across habitats. *Diversity and Distributions*, 15(1), 98–107.
- Davis, P. H., Mill, R. R., & Tan, K. (1988). *Flora of Turkey and the East Aegean Islands* (Vol. 10). Edinburgh University Press.
- Essl, F., Dullinger, S., Rabitsch, W., Hulme, P. E., Hülber, K., Jarošík, V., ... Pyšek, P. (2011). Socioeconomic legacy yields an invasion debt. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 108(1), 203–207.
- Florentine, S., Humphries, T., & Chauhan, B. S. (2021). *Erigeron bonariensis*, *Erigeron canadensis*, and *Erigeron sumatrensis*. In B. S. Chauhan (Ed.), *Biology and management of problematic crop weed species*. Academic Press.
- Galkina, M. A., & Vinogradova, Y. K. (2020). Invasive species of *Erigeron* sect. *Conyza* in the Mediterranean and their hybridogenic activity. *Biology Bulletin*, 47(1), 40–48.
- Hao, J., Qiang, S., Liu, Q., & Cao, F. (2009). Reproductive traits associated with invasiveness in *Conyza sumatrensis*. *Journal of Systematics and Evolution*, 47(3), 245–254.
- Heap, I. (2025). The International Herbicide-Resistant Weed Database. WeedScience.org. (Accessed 28 November 2025)
- Higgins, S., & Richardson, D. (1996). A review of models of alien plant spread. *Ecological Modelling*, 87(1–3), 249–265.
- Kadriaj, B. (2024). The invasive alien plants of the vascular flora in the eastern region of Kosovo (Doctoral thesis). University of Prishtina.
- Kadriaj, B., Berisha, N., Krasniqi, E., & Millaku, F. (2023). Invasive alien plant species (IAPS) in the eastern region of Kosovo: A preliminary list. *Ecologia Balkanica*, 15(2), 22–31.
- Kalusová, V., Čeplová, N., Danihelka, J., Večeřa, M., Pyšek, P., Albert, A., ... Axmanová, I. (2024). Alien plants of Europe. *Preslia*, 96(2), 149–182.
- Lambdon, P. W., Pyšek, P., Basnou, C., Hejda, M., Arianoutsou, M., Essl, F., ... Hulme, P. E. (2008). Alien flora of Europe: Species diversity, temporal trends, geographical patterns and research needs. *Preslia*, 80, 101–149.
- Liendo, D., García-Mijangos, I., Biurrun, I., & Campos, J. A. (2021). Annual weedy species of *Erigeron* in the northern Iberian Peninsula: A review. *Mediterranean Botany*, 42, e67649.
- Lorenzetti, J. B., Albrecht, A. J. P., Albrecht, L. P., Danilussi, M. T. Y., Barroso, A. A. M., Bauer, F. E., Silva, A. F. M., & Marchi, C. S. (2025). Interference of *Conyza sumatrensis* on grain yield of soybean cultivars. *Revista Facultad Nacional de Agronomía Medellín*, 78(1), 10967–10975.
- Marshall, J. B. (1973). *Conyza* taxa found in Britain. *Watsonia*, 9, 372–373.

- Maslo, S., & Šarić, Š. (2020). *Erigeron sumatrensis* Retz. (Compositae), a recently recognized invasive alien species in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Glasnik Hrvatskog Botaničkog Društva, 8(2), 88–93.
- Millaku, F., Kadriaj, B., & Berisha, N. (2024). First records of *Rudbeckia hirta* and *Oenothera glazioviana* in the flora of Kosovo. Botanica, 117–124.
- Milović, M. (2004). Naturalised species from the genus *Conyza* Less. (Asteraceae) in Croatia. Acta Botanica Croatica, 63(2), 147–170.
- Nesom, G. L. (2018). *Erigeron floribundus* and *E. sumatrensis* (Asteraceae) in the USA and Mexico. Phytoneuron, 27, 1–19.
- Nikolić, T. (2020). Flora Croatica: vaskularna flora Republike Hrvatske (Vol. 2). Alfa d.d.
- Pattison, Z., Minderman, J., Boon, P. J., & Willby, N. (2016). Twenty years of change in riverside vegetation: What role have invasive alien plants played? Applied Vegetation Science, 20(3), 422–434.
- Poldini, L., & Kaligarić, M. (2000). *Bidens pilosa* and *Conyza sumatrensis*, two new naturalised species in the flora of Slovenia. Annales, Series Historia Naturalis, 10, 77–80.
- POWO. (2025). Plants of the World Online. Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew. (Accessed 6 December 2025)
- Pruski, J. F., & Sancho, G. (2006). *Conyza sumatrensis* var. *leiotheca* (Compositae: Astereae), a new combination for a common neotropical weed. Novon, 16(1), 96–101.
- Pyšek, P., Hulme, P. E., Simberloff, D., Bacher, S., Blackburn, T. M., Carlton, J. T., ... Richardson, D. M. (2020). Scientists' warning on invasive alien species. Biological Reviews, 95(6), 1511–1534.
- Pyšek, P., Jarošík, V., Hulme, P. E., Pergl, J., Hejda, M., Schaffner, U., & Vilà, M. (2012). A global assessment of invasive plant impacts on resident species, communities and ecosystems: The interaction of impact measures, invading species' traits and environment. Global Change Biology, 18, 1725–1737.
- Pyšek, P., Lambdon, P. W., Arianoutsou, M., Kühn, I., Pino, J., & Winter, M. (2009). Alien vascular plants of Europe. In Handbook of Alien Species in Europe (pp. 43–61). Springer.
- Rasool, N., Reshi, Z. A., Khasa, D. P., Roshan, M., & Shah, M. A. (2016). Invasion by *Conyza sumatrensis* alters soil microbial community structure in urban ecosystems. Ecological Processes, 5, 10.
- Riera, M., Pino, J., & Melero, Y. (2021). Impact of introduction pathways on the spread and geographical distribution of alien species: Implications for preventive management in Mediterranean ecosystems. Diversity and Distributions, 27(6), 1019–1034.
- Seebens, H., Bacher, S., Blackburn, T. M., Capinha, C., Dawson, W., Dullinger, S., ... Essl, F. (2021). Projecting the continental accumulation of alien species through to 2050. Global Change Biology, 27(5), 970–982.
- Šilc, U., Vrbničanin, S., Božić, D., Čarni, A., & Stevanović, Z. (2012). Alien plant species and factors of invasiveness of anthropogenic vegetation in the Northwestern Balkans — A phytosociological approach. Open Life Sciences, 7(4), 720–730.
- Sîrbu, C., Oprea, A., Doroftei, M., & Covaliov, S. (2023). New data on the distribution and invasion status of some alien plants in Romania. Journal of Plant Development, 30, 17–32.
- Stešević, D., Caković, D., & Jovanović, S. (2014). The urban flora of Podgorica (Montenegro, SE Europe). Ecologica Montenegrina, Suppl. 1, 1–171.
- Stešević, D., & Petrović, D. (2010). Preliminary list of plant invaders in Montenegro. Biologica Nyssana, 1(1–2), 35–42.
- Tutin, T. G., Heywood, V. H., Burges, N. A., Moore, D. M., Valentine, D. H., Walters, S. M., & Webb, D. A. (1976). Flora Europaea, Volume 4: Plantaginaceae to Compositae (and Rubiaceae). Cambridge University Press.
- Vilà, M., Espinar, J. L., Hejda, M., Hulme, P. E., Jarošík, V., Maron, J. L., Pergl, J., Schaffner, U., Sun, Y., & Pyšek, P. (2011). Ecological impacts of invasive alien plants: A meta-analysis of their effects on species, communities and ecosystems. Ecology Letters, 14, 702–708.
- Vladimirov, V. (2009). *Erigeron sumatrensis* (Asteraceae): A recently recognized alien species in the Bulgarian flora. Phytologia Balcanica, 15(3), 361–365.
- Vladimirov, V., Matevski, V., Bancheva, S., Delcheva, M., Kostadinovski, M., & Čušterevska, R. (2016). First report of *Erigeron sumatrensis* (Asteraceae) for the flora of the Republic of Macedonia. Flora Mediterranea, 26, 203–207.
- Vladimirov, V., & Petrova, A. (2023). Alien species of vascular plants first reported for Bulgaria after 2000. Phytologia Balcanica, 29(3), 461–474.
- Vrbničanin, S., Karadžić, B., & Dajić-Stevanović, Z. (2004). Adventive and invasive weed species in Serbia. Acta Herbológica, 13(1), 1–12.
- Wang, A., Wu, H., Zhu, X., & Lin, J. (2018). Species identification of *Conyza bonariensis* assisted by chloroplast genome sequencing. Frontiers in Genetics, 9, 374.
- Zajac, A., Tokarska-Guzik, B., & Zajac, M. (2011). The role of rivers and streams in the migration of alien plants into the Polish Carpathians. Biodiversity Research and Conservation, 23, 43–56.
- Zelnik, I. (2012). The presence of invasive alien plant species in different habitats: Case study from Slovenia. Acta Biologica Slovenica, 55, 25–38.